

THE PECULIARITIES OF PROFESSIONAL MOBILITY IN ACQUISITION OF AGRICULTURE

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ABSTRACT

In the recent years, there are a lot of changes have been done in the education system in our country. The engineering students are trying to gain theoretical knowledge and practical experience from the beginning of studies at the university because of economic labor market and needs of students. Therefore, the engineering students are in need of professional mobility to accomplish from the first course of study at the university.

Furthermore, there are a lot of ideas, discussions were done among the scholars according to the peculiarities of professional mobility and its role in the society.

Introduction

In the area of pedagogical sciences, teaching is essential. Teaching professional subjects to the engineering students in the area of agriculture is important because of their future goal orientation. Furthermore, dual teaching is accomplishing in some universities of Uzbekistan, especially, technical universities where the students are able to study and work simultaneously. There are a lot of advantages of dual teaching in education system. The students may gain wider theoretical knowledge and put their knowledge into action at workplaces. This methodology is able to grow their ideas and interests to the area of agriculture. Agriculture is broadly industry area of science where the engineering students may learn cultivation, agronomy, husbandry, gardening, transportation, storage, hydrology. It encompasses a broad range of activities, from cultivating food and cash crops and raising livestock to forestry and aquaculture, forming the foundation of human civilization by providing essential resources. Therefore, the engineering students need to know professional mobility in this area of science. This paper highlights integration of study with practice for the engineering students as professional mobility as well as peculiarities of professional mobility.

Literature Review The independent use of the term "professional mobility" in scientific literature dates back to the middle of the last century, when it was interpreted as "changing different occupations or professions" (S. Lipset, R. Benedicks). Since the 1980s, research into this phenomenon has been conducted regularly both abroad and in Russian science. Furthermore, the conditions for the formation of professional mobility are revealed in the

works of A. M. Vaschenko (future officers), I. U. Zabirov (managers of industrial enterprises), E. A. Ivanchenko (future economists), S. E. Kaplina (future engineers), L. A. Amirova I. V. Nikulina, L. V. Goryunova, Yu. Yu. Dvoretzkaya (higher education teacher), B. M. Igoshev, A. A. Nikitina, R. N. Prima, V. A. Slastenin (future teacher), S. K. Savitsky (mechanical engineering specialist), I. V. Shpektorenko (civil servant), etc. The influence of professional mobility on professional development and the formation of a professionally successful person was studied by S. A. Kugel, R. T. Nasybulin, K. Popper, I. Prigogine, I. L. Smirnova, I. T. Frolov and others. Sharing the opinion of L. N. Lesokhina, L. I. Ribnikova examines the concept of professional mobility from two perspectives:

1) on the one hand, it is a change in position caused by external conditions, namely: a lack of jobs, low wages, workers' lack of domestic stability, etc., which necessitates their adaptation to real life positions;

2) on the other hand, professional mobility can be seen as internal freedom, self-improvement of the individual, based on stable values and the need for self-organization, self-determination and self-development, the ability to quickly respond to changes in society thanks to education and professional competence.

The methodology of professional mobility in education and social-philosophical and psychological-professional theoretical ideas were carried out by following scholars (V.I.Baydenko, V.A.Bolotov, S.I.Ivanova, N.D.Nikandrovs). They also conducted a research concerning on professional mobility as social and personal competence.

Some Uzbek scholars (A.R.Xodjabayev, N.A.Muslimov, Q.T.Olimov, U.I.Inoyatov, B.X.Xodjayev, X.F.Rashidov, O'.Q.Tolipov, U.Sh.Begimqulov, M.B.Urazova, J.A.Hamidov, O.X.Turaqulov, Z.K.Ismailova, D.O.Himmataliev, O.A.Quysinov) carried out a research on the methodological basis of professional mobility and its fundamental essence.

Essential peculiarities of professional mobility Any changes in social life lead to certain changes in the vocational education system. The globalization of education and professional mobility around the world raises the problem of ensuring the mobility of professionals in a new era. Furthermore, one of the timeless features of professionalism is its mobility, which, in turn, makes it necessary to adapt to changes in the internal, personal-psychological, and external practical activities for any person. Consequently, today, the employer is increasingly demanding for the candidate who can quickly and perfectly master innovative technology, ensure the expected results, strive to improve his professional activity immediately, demonstrate innovative behavior, and also is able quickly adapt to a changing environment. What's more, in a competitive environment, it is becoming increasingly important for specialists at all levels to acquire additional skills or knowledge, continuously improve their skills. This increases professional mobility of the engineering students of agriculture. The ability of a sociologist to be professionally mobile, to work in conditions of constant change, to adapt to innovation or a flexible economy requires study as a sociological problem.

There are some essential peculiarities in understanding professional mobility:

1 in the context of modern innovation, the professional mobility of person creates the possibility of making sociological generalizations about the tasks related to meeting the need for quality work around the world and the corresponding information; being aware of conditions of workplace and educational context of that industry; being skillful to that branch of agriculture where he/she is a student to acquire; being sociable with the farmers in that area

of agriculture during accomplishing professional mobility; being able to have theoretical idea of professional mobility.

Conclusion

Today there are a lot of changes in the education system of our country. One of them is teaching agriculture integrally at the University and workplace-farms, plants, factories, food fields, cultivation fields. For such reason, professional mobility is foremost in education system which may help improve the engineering students' not only theoretical knowledge but also practical experience in acquisition of education 1 in the field of agriculture. Professional mobility also increases the engineering students' fundamental knowledge while practicing in the workplaces. That's why, we should set up project in accordance with professional mobility. Professional mobility informs new information about the subjects and strengthens gained knowledge, and the students are able to advance in their specialty as a professional specialist

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